

IMI2 Project No 777372 - RESOLUTE

Research empowerment on solute carriers

WP8 – Knowledge integration and data management

D8.5 RESOLUTE database

Lead contributor	Ulrich Goldmann (1 – CeMM Research Center for Molecular Medicine of the Austrian Academy of Sciences) ugoldmann@cemm.at
Other contributors	Vitaly Sedlyarov (1 – CeMM Research Center for Molecular Medicine of the Austrian Academy of Sciences) vsedlyarov@cemm.at

Due date	30 June 2019
Delivery date	30 June 2019
Deliverable type	DEC ¹
Dissemination level	PU ²

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V0.1	12 June 2019	First draft of document structure (UG)
V0.2	13 June 2019	Added screenshots, figures and introduction (UG)
V0.3	14 June 2019	Added paragraphs on Motivation, Structure and Implementation (UG/VS)
V1.0	30 June 2019	Final Version (approved by all partners)

¹ Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

² Public, fully open.

Table of Contents

Publishable Summary	3
Introduction	3
Motivation	4
Conceptual Structure	5
File Repository	5
Reagents / Samples Database	5
Experiments / Analyses Database	5
Data Identifiers	6
Data Sustainability	6
Implementation	6
Storage server	6
Back End Architecture	7
Front End Architecture	7
Status and Outlook	7

Publishable Summary

Solute carrier (SLC) membrane transport proteins control essential physiological functions, including nutrient uptake, ion transport, and waste removal. SLCs can be seen as gatekeepers and include 446 membrane proteins arranged into 65 families. SLCs are the second-largest family of membrane proteins in the human genome and are vital for maintaining homeostasis in the body and in individual cells. RESOLUTE’s ambitious aim is to assign biochemical and biological functions to as many SLC genes as possible using a systematic approach. The RESOLUTE database forms the single point of entry for collecting, storing and querying results of all experiments and analyses as well as information on reagents generated throughout the RESOLUTE project. Moreover, the RESOLUTE database will also serve as a tool for dissemination of published results and reagents to the scientific community.

Introduction

Virtually every individual task of the RESOLUTE project depends on or produces data. On the one hand, publicly available data is collected and compiled into the RESOLUTE knowledgebase (Deliverable 8.4). A majority of data, on the other hand, is newly generated, processed and analysed throughout the project. This process is supported by the RESOLUTE database. Both resources, the RESOLUTE knowledgebase and the RESOLUTE database, are accessible from the RESOLUTE web portal at <https://re-solute.eu> (Deliverable 8.6; see Figure 1).

While the RESOLUTE knowledgebase is a SLC centric database of publicly available knowledge, the RESOLUTE database (Figure 2) is an experiment and data set centric database of all results generated in the RESOLUTE project. It represents the central point of data management, data curation and data access throughout the RESOLUTE project. This report summarizes the structure, the implementation choices, the current state and next steps planned.

Figure 1. RESOLUTE web portal.

Figure 2. Design prototype for the web interface to the RESOLUTE database.

Motivation

The RESOLUTE database is designed to support the implementation of Data Management Plan (Deliverable 8.1) in the following major aspects:

- 1) Logistics of physical entities. Tracking of creation, annotation, quality control, storage and distribution of samples and reagents.
- 2) Recording information about experiments and analysis procedures. To ensure reproducibility of research data, consistent description of workflows used to produce the data is required.
- 3) Storage of data and linking metadata. Metadata are stored in the database and linked to the data files on the storage server.
- 4) Implementation of FAIR principles on the data. An identifier schema, standardized metadata and controlled vocabularies implement the Findability principle. Infrastructure and database design providing web- as well as API-access ensure that data are Accessible to both humans and machines. Data are referenced to other data and metadata conforming with the Interoperability principle. Data are stored in open, community accepted formats and linked to corresponding metadata, which enables wide data Reusability.
- 5) Ensure data security. Data security is central issue for the database design. It is implemented through the following principles: (1) OAuth protocol for secure access to consortium internal data, (2) traffic encryption for secure data transfer.
- 6) Separated access. While all consortium members have full access to all data sets, a dedicated area of the database will allow open access to publicly released data sets.

Until the end of the year, the RESOLUTE database will become the major resource in supporting the researches in sharing reagents, data, experimental and analytical workflows. In future, it will also serve as a portal to disseminate published RESOLUTE results to the scientific community.

Conceptual Structure

A multitude of types of data and metadata is going to be produced in the course of the RESOLUTE project, ranging from primary data over integrative data analyses to reagents, analysis tools and workflows. The database has to accommodate all these data types with their specific needs for metadata and relations.

The overall structure of the RESOLUTE database can be split into 3 major parts: a file repository to store raw files, a relational database to annotate physical entities and a relational database to annotate virtual entities.

File Repository

Raw files make up a majority of the required disk space but are typically further processed to smaller, more interpretable summaries. Therefore, raw files will not enter the relational database but are deposited at the storage server and are linked to corresponding preceding or succeeding entries in the databases, supporting data provenance.

Reagents / Samples Database

Over the course of 5 years, RESOLUTE will generate a significant amount of reagents and samples of different kind. The reagents are generated at different sites and transferred between the locations. To keep track of the reagent related metadata, quality control information, storage and shipment logistics, a database is established. The database is implemented as relational database and allows users to retrieve information, request transfer or enter new items.

Experiments / Analyses Database

This part of the RESOLUTE database features a relational database to keep track of experiments and analyses. While in an *experiment*, a *sample* is *measured* according to a certain *protocol* to create a *result*, in an *analysis*, a *data* set is *processed* according to a certain *protocol* to create a *result* (see Figure 3). This flexible setup allows to accommodate experimental results produced with all the various experimental technologies that will be applied in the RESOLUTE project.

Figure 3. Abstract overview schema of relations between entities in the database.

Data Identifiers

Each entry in the RESOLUTE database will be assigned a RESOLUTE identifier. The identifier schema was designed following recently published recommendations for the field of life sciences¹ (see Deliverable 8.1 for more details). By linking data files, reagents, experiments, analyses and results the RESOLUTE database also implements data lineage and data provenance tracking.

Data Sustainability

All data entering the RESOLUTE database will be stored for the course of the project. The RESOLUTE data- and knowledgebase will be supported by CeMM for at least 5 more years after the end of the project. To support long-term preservation, the RESOLUTE database builds on open, community accepted standards for data structure, data formats, and metadata formats, making data transferable to domain specific, certified public data repositories.

Implementation

Implementation of the RESOLUTE database follows a client-server architecture and can be split into 3 subprojects: a file repository to store results, a back end which handles the application logic to annotate and link entities in a relational database, as well as a front end to access and visualize the data (web application, API). So far, the web portal is the only front end under development but additional front ends (e.g. KNIME workflow nodes) can build on the structured API. The underlying hardware infrastructure is provided by the CeMM IT department. Employment of virtual machines allows for maximal flexibility and scalability. The RESOLUTE database is built on open-source software wherever possible. Figure 4 shows a summary of the overall implementation architecture.

Figure 4. Overview on RESOLUTE database infrastructure and technology stack.

Storage server

A storage server with a total capacity of up to 300 TB is set up at the local IT infrastructure of CeMM and managed by the CeMM IT department. As access to the CeMM storage server is strictly restricted and available

¹ McMurry JA, et al. Identifiers for the 21st century: How to design, provision, and reuse persistent identifiers to maximize utility and impact of life science data. PLoS Biol. 2017 Jun 29;15(6):e2001414. doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.2001414.

only from within the CeMM intranet, special means of secure data access and secure data transfer have to be established to allow participants to submit or access internal data, and to allow public users to view and download published data.

Back End Architecture

For the back end architecture, we built on modern, but tested technologies. Application logic is running on a Node.js server (open source) and implemented in the TypeScript 3 language (open source). The data model is defined in classes, and we use TypeORM (open source) to map the model to the entity-relationship structure of the database. The actual database is served by a PostgreSQL (open source) instance. TypeORM also provides easy, object-oriented access to the database for the application. The front end is provided a GraphQL (open source) API which is partially auto-generated by a PostGraphile (open source) instance. The use of Docker (open source) enables a frictionless deployment from the development server to the production server for updates on the application logic, the data access layer or the database server.

Authentication for accessing non-public areas of the RESOLUTE database is provided by a Microsoft Azure Active Directory (via Office365), which is already employed by the consortium for communication and data sharing (see also Data Management Plan; deliverable 8.1).

Front End Architecture

The front end is based on Vue.js (open source), a framework for component-based web user interfaces. We follow a *serverless* design, meaning that the client runs most of the application logic and the back end is only requested for specific services such as authentication or data queries. The Apollo GraphQL client (open source) is used for communication to the server.

Adhering to state-of-the-art web standards (HTML5, ES6, CSS3), the front end is compatible to all modern web browsers. We test compatibility with Mozilla Firefox (open source) and with Google Chrome.

Status and Outlook

The RESOLUTE database is still under development. A first alpha version of the RESOLUTE database back end with limited functionality is already in use since month 11 (i.e. May 2019), but there is no front end in place yet. Development is currently focused on supporting reagent handling. Based on the first transcriptomics and proteomics data sets that have been produced recently, we also started to implement an initial version of the web interface (Figure 2). Release of the first – consortium internal – beta version is planned for month 16 (i.e. Oct 2019). Release of the first public beta version is planned together with the official release of the RESOLUTE web portal (deliverable D8.6) at month 18 (i.e. Dec 2019).

We expect a significant amount of data to be generated within the RESOLUTE project over the next 4 years (see Data Management Plan; deliverable D8.1), and therefore flexibility and scalability of the RESOLUTE database architecture and infrastructure is key. Major refactoring cycles are planned twice a year in order to adapt to new requirements arising from new data types or to resolve potential issues.